

Waste animal bone as a low-cost precursor for bonechar in xylene adsorption

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the bonechar prepared from diverse animal waste bones by microwave pyrolysis, with the aim of determining its chemical and structural properties and application potential for xylene adsorption. It was revealed that the type of raw bone itself is more significant for the pyrolysis bonechar yield than the microwave power. Beef bones produced the highest amount of bonechar (~60 wt%), which can be attributed to the high levels of fixed carbon (~4 wt%) and ash (~50 wt%) in the raw material. The bonechar is, in fact, a composite material composed of dominant hydroxyapatite and minor carbon, showing a well-defined mesoporous-macroporous structure with S_{BET} and V_{net} decreasing as the Ca/P molar ratio in hydroxyapatite increases. Xylene adsorption capacity of the bonechar is affected by the inter-play of following factors: the porous structure, fixed carbon content, degree of carbon graphitisation and the presence of surface CaO and Ca^{2+} cations. These findings are supported by force-field based molecular modelling. Bonechars prepared from fresh beef bones exhibited the highest xylene adsorption capacity, characterized by the medium porosity ($S_{\text{BET}} \approx 95 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), high fixed carbon content (~16 wt%), pronounced graphitisation ($I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}} \approx 1.00\text{--}1.06$) and elevated surface content of CaO (~72 at % of present as CaO). Overall, the order of bonechars adsorption capacities from various animal bones in xylene adsorption is following: fresh beef bones ($\sim 46 \text{ mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) > boiled beef bones ~ boiled pork bones ~ boiled chicken bones ($14\text{--}24 \text{ mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$).

1. Introduction

Food industries, especially meat processing plants and slaughterhouses, produce huge amount of animal by-products [1]. According to the regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council No. 1774/2002, animal by-products are defined as “*entire bodies or parts of animals or products of animal origin (referred to in articles 4, 5 and 6 of this regulation) and not intended for human consumption, including ova, embryos and semen*” [2].

The global number of livestock is ~4.89 billion including all species of cattle, sheep, pigs, and goats, and ~27.88 billion of various types of poultry. More than 3.5 million tons per year of meat and bone meal are

produced in total in the European Union [3]. The processing of this huge number of livestock and poultry worldwide generates up to several million tons of solid waste, which ends up in the environment without any intervention [4]. In addition to the slaughter of animals for human consumption, the waste animal by-products are also generated during the disposal of dead animal bodies, the production of animal products, and the performance of disease controls. The slaughterhouse industry produces ~130 billion kg of waste animal bones annually (of which >10% in European countries). This can be considered an alarming environmental burden. Waste bones of a slaughtered animal represent ~18 wt% of its total weight [5]. This and other slaughter waste are deposited in landfills or disposed of in rendering plants. Since the Bovine

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Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) crisis, the addition of waste bones as a protein-rich product into cattle feed has been restricted in Europe. Other countries such as Canada and USA have also adopted laws preventing the use of specific risk materials in animal feed production [3]. EU legislation for safety rules mandates the processing of all bone waste from slaughterhouse in rendering plants. The fees charged by commercial rendering plants for the disposal of animal waste represent an additional cost for the meat production. In 2025, slaughterhouses in Czech Republic paid $\sim 0.4 \text{ €}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ for bone waste disposal [6].

The most advantageous way of dealing with waste animal by-product is the environmentally friendly transformation into useful and valuable materials, and composting, vermicomposting, biogas production, thermochemical processes, or value-added products formation have been extensively investigated [4].

One of the less used options for the waste animal-by products is a microwave pyrolysis involving a thermochemical conversion in oxygen-free atmosphere into gas, liquid and solid products. It is more advantageous compared to conventional pyrolysis due to its rapid, selective and volumetric heating, thereby increasing the reaction speed. Resulting solid phase – bonechar, is a carbon-based material with favourable textural properties (due to natural porous structure of bones), with high surface functionality and cations exchange ability which is efficient for adsorption [7]. The multi-phase composition of the bonechar containing graphitic carbon and calcium phosphate/hydroxyapatite results in the ability to simultaneously remove both organic pollutants and metals. Graphitic carbon in bonechar is studied for organic molecules adsorption (fuchsine dye [7], toluene [8], phenol [9]), and calcium phosphate together with hydroxyapatite have very good performance for removal of fluorides [10–13], sulphur [14], or arsenic [12]. Hydroxyapatite is especially effective with bivalent cations such as Pb(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) [15,16] due to cation exchange between the metals and the originally present Ca(II) in the lattice. Hydroxyapatite also has anion exchange ability and good sorption efficiency [17]. Moreover, it is highly stable under oxidation-reduction conditions with good buffering capacity [17]. The combination of these two phases makes bonechar very versatile for environmental utilization compared to various biochars containing only carbonaceous part [15].

Efficiency in obtaining high-value products was the reason for pilot-scale testing of microwave pyrolysis (Thailand [18], Norwegian University [19], University of Minnesota [20], Resynergi USA [21], China [22]) and its introduction into industrial production (Micro-fuel (Norway), Tech-wave (Italy), Ellsin Environment, Pyrowave (Canada), HY Microwave Technology (China). However, these activities are focused on plastic and agricultural waste. Almost no studies dealing with preparation of bonechar using microwave pyrolysis of waste animal bones have been published yet (see e.g. no mention of it in the review by Piccirillo [15]). Although the use of waste animal bones as a raw material for adsorption could be a useful and safe way of disposing these wastes [15], there is a knowledge gap about the effect of the microwave conditions on textural, structural, and adsorption properties of produced bonechar from different types of bones without activation. Moreover, the utilization of the microwave pyrolysis could help achieve real circular economy that converts products at the end of their life cycle into raw materials for reuse [23].

According to our knowledge, only few studies devoted to the adsorption of xylenes on bonechar from air was already published outside our group. Tala et al. [24] and Feo [25], however, used bonechar prepared by conventional pyrolysis. In general, bonechar prepared by microwave pyrolysis is still an underexplored area, and its use for adsorption of volatile organic compounds (VOC) is not explored at all. At the same time, removing VOC from the environment is not a negligible topic, since VOC, released as a gases from fuel combustion or chemical, pharmaceutical or tobacco industries, to name a few [26], have often caused serious health impact like allergy, eye irritation, headache, cough, dizziness, vomiting and lack of concentration [27]. Significant quantity of VOC with anthropogenic origins are annually released in the

atmosphere ($142 \text{ tgc}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) [28]. Benzene series VOCs including xylenes are commonly used and emitted by industry and may lead to diseases in human such as leukaemia and myelodysplastic syndrome [26]. Therefore, effective technologies to eliminate benzene series VOCs from waste gases are urgently needed. Adsorption technique is a low-cost, efficient, and simple process strategy, as both the adsorbent and the captured VOC can be regenerated and reused [26]. Currently, carbonaceous materials with high porosity and high surface area, i.e. activated carbon, carbon nanotubes, biochar, etc., are used for VOC adsorption [27].

Based on the above, this study is focused on producing bonechar via microwave pyrolysis of waste bones of three animal species (beef, pork, and chicken) at various microwave power (200, 400, 600 W) for 30 min. Since different types of bones contain different proportion of inorganic and organic phases, pyrolysis led to bonechars with different composition and characteristics affecting the bonechar performance. For this reason, chemical, textural, and structural properties of bonechars were studied, and xylene adsorption from air on the most prospective bonechars was thoroughly investigated in order to describe the adsorption capacity-determining factors, a reveal and commercial application potential of bonechars for VOCs abatement.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw feedstock

Waste animal bones-raw material (WAB-RM) from beef and pork were supplied by company Těšínské jatky, s.r.o. (Ceský Těšín, Czech Republic). WAB-RM from chickens were delivered by company DIEMA s.r.o. (Frýdek-Místek, Czech Republic).

The bones were pre-treated in boiling water for 3 h to remove fat and proteins, and subsequently dried at 105 °C overnight. The material was further treated by cryogenic grinding in a laboratory knife mill Testchem-LMN 180 (ANMAT, Czech Republic) to grain size $< 5 \text{ mm}$. Sample of boiled waste animal bones was denoted as follows: beef boiled bones (BB-RM), pork boiled bones (PB-RM) and chicken boiled bones (CB-RM).

Part of raw beef bones was separated, without cooking treated by grinding in a laboratory knife mill Testchem-LMN 180 (ANMAT, Czech Republic) and sieved to a size $< 5 \text{ mm}$. This sample was denoted as beef fresh bones (BF-RM).

Commercial carbons blacks under the name MAC6 I K_2CO_3 5% and MAC6 I KOH 5% were supplied by company Resorbent, s.r.o. (Ostrava, Czech Republic). The materials were sieved to a grain size of 1.5–2.5 mm.

2.2. Preparation of bonechar by microwave pyrolysis

The microwave (MW) pyrolysis apparatus used in this study (see Fig. S1 in Supplementary material) consisted of the commercial lab-modified MW oven LG EDG (3) adjusted for emplacement of fixed bed glass reactor (4) followed by a glass tube, condenser (1), impingers (7, 8, 9) and gasometer (10). Treated WAB-RM (50 g) was enriched with 2 g of carbon (prepared by conventional pyrolysis of WAB-RM at 800 °C for 1 h and heating rate of $10 \text{ °C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ which is needed to start the MW pyrolysis reaction). Set MW powers were 200, 400 or 600 W for 30 min. After cooling in water cooler (5), liquid phase was collected in a flask (6), and the amount of gas phase was determined by a gasometer after cleaning in 3 impingers (with water and acetone). Solid phase – bonechar (denoted generally as WAB-C) was kept in a fixed bed glass reactor (4). Before each experiment, the whole apparatus was purged by 5 L of N_2 . The mass balance of pyrolytic products was determined based on the weight of solid and liquid phases, with the gas representing the remainder up to 100 wt%.

Each bonechar prepared from waste animal bones was denoted as WAB-C;P; where WAB represents type of bones (i.e. BF, BB, PB, or CB),

and P represents the MW power used (200, 400, or 600 W). E.g. bonechar prepared from beef fresh bones at 200 W is denoted as BF-C;200.

2.3. Adsorption capacity of xylene

To evaluate xylene adsorption, a laboratory-scale experimental apparatus was employed. Bonechars with a particle size fraction of 1.5–2.5 mm was packed into a fixed-bed adsorber. Compressed air supplied from a central gas distribution system was regulated by a mass flow controller (GFC, Aalborg) to maintain a constant flow rate of 2.5 L·min⁻¹. A manometer and rotameter were installed for operational control and verification of the selected conditions. The air stream was heated to 160 °C using a heating belt, exceeding the boiling point of xylene (≈140 °C) to ensure complete evaporation. Liquid xylene (0.027 ml·min⁻¹) was introduced into the heated air stream via an HPLC pump (LC-20AD), positioned centrally within the heating zone, to achieve a target concentration of 1000 ppm. The xylene feed was supplied from an external reservoir. Three-way valves enabled control of the gas flow through individual branches of the system, allowing either passage of VOC-laden air through the adsorption column or diversion through a bypass line. The adsorption column (Simax glass, length of 440 mm, internal diameter of 25 mm), constituted the core of the experimental setup. It was packed with 2.5 g of bonechar, supported by quartz wool (~ 0.3 g, ROTH Karlsruhe, Germany) placed above and below the adsorbent bed. Additionally, glass beads (30 glass balls with 2.5 mm diameter, ROTH Karlsruhe, Germany) were positioned at both ends of the bed to ensure uniform gas distribution. The outlet xylene concentration was continuously monitored using an online FTIR analyzer (Antaris™ IGS Gas Analyzer, Thermo Scientific). For all adsorption experiments, technical-grade xylene (VWR International s.r.o., Stříbrná Skalice, Czech Republic) was used. The mixture consisted of o-xylene (39.8%), m-xylene (18.4%), p-xylene (26.9%), and ethylbenzene (16.9%), with composition determined by the production process. This technical mixture of xylene isomers, containing also ethylbenzene, was employed as a model pollutant to simulate realistic industrial conditions. Adsorption capacity was determined using breakthrough curve analysis based on FTIR monitoring of xylene concentration at the column outlet. Due to the limitations of the FTIR method and the absence of specific calibration standards, it was not possible to differentiate quantitatively between the adsorption of individual xylene isomers and ethylbenzene. Although slight differences in adsorption affinity may arise from their distinct boiling points (o-xylene: 144.4 °C; m-xylene: 139 °C; p-xylene: 138.4 °C; ethylbenzene: 136 °C), this potential chromatographic effect was not considered and was therefore neglected in the evaluation of adsorption performance.

The adsorption capacity was calculated as follows:

$$q = \frac{V_t x}{m} \quad (1)$$

$$t_t = \int_0^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{x}{x_0}\right) dt \quad (2)$$

q is the adsorption capacity of bonechar (ml_{xylene}·g⁻¹, mg_{xylene}·g⁻¹), \dot{V} is the flow rate of the reaction mixture (2.5 L·min⁻¹), t_t is the time period, given by numerical integration using the trapezoidal method (min), x is the actual xylene molar fraction in the gas phase, m is the bonechar weight (~2.5 g), x_0 is the initial xylene molar fraction in the gas phase 1000 ppm.

Calculation of the actual molar fraction using the integral of the trapezoidal method:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_1} f(x) dx \approx h \frac{f(x_0) + f(x_1)}{2} = \frac{h}{2} (f(x_0) + f(x_1)) \quad (3)$$

Due to limitations of FTIR, including the lack of specific calibration standards and significant overlap of the characteristic absorption bands,

quantitative differentiation between the individual xylenes and ethylbenzene was not possible. The aromatic C–H (3000–3100 cm⁻¹) and aliphatic C–H (2800–3000 cm⁻¹) bands are the same for all isomers, but the aliphatic C–H band may differ in detail depending on the presence of an ethyl or methyl group [29,30]. The C=C aromatic ring (1600–1650 cm⁻¹) is similar for all isomers, but the deformation vibration (1450–1500 cm⁻¹) bands will overlap [31].

To test the stability of bonechar during regeneration at 160 °C, fresh samples were placed in the reactor and fresh preheated air was let flow through it for 24 h (twice as long as the regeneration process). The properties of fresh bonechar and bonechar after regeneration were determined and compared to avoid any changes.

The relative error of adsorption curve of commercial black coal measurements determined from repeated experiments was 4%.

2.4. Characterisation methods

Amount of proteins, dry matter, fat, sugar, fibre, and starch in WAB-RM was determined in the commercial accredited laboratory (Ekocentrum Ovalab, Martinovská 3248/166, Ostrava-Martinov, Czech Republic), holder of ČSN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 certificate No. 690/2020.

Proximate analysis was done for WAB-RM and WAB-C according to the ASTM D7582 standard (LECO, TGA 701) consisted of the moisture (wt%), volatile matter (wt%), fixed carbon (wt%), and ash content (wt%) determination. Ultimate analysis was measured according to the Standard ASTM D3172–13 and D5373–16 (LECO CHNS 628, LECO AC 350) were done for WAB-RM and WAB-C as well.

Thermogravimetric curves of WAB-RM were measured using SDT 600 thermogravimeter (TA Instruments, USA). All experiments were carried out in crucibles (α-Al₂O₃) in a dynamic N₂ atmosphere (flow rate 100 cm³·min⁻¹) at 1000 °C (heating rate 10 °C·min⁻¹).

Nitrogen physisorptions on WAB-C samples at 77 K were performed on a 3Flex instrument (Micromeritics, USA). The measurements were preceded by drying and degassing the samples (~0.05–0.08 g) at 350 °C under vacuum (< 1 Pa) for 24 h. Specific surface area, S_{BET} , was determined based on the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) theory [32] for a range of relative pressures $p/p_0 = 0.05–0.25$. The micropore volume, V_{micro} , and mesopore surface area, S_{meso} , were evaluated by the t-plot method using the standard Carbon Black STSA isotherm. Total pore volume, V_{net} , was determined from the N₂ adsorption isotherm for a maximum relative pressure of $p/p_0 = 0.99$. Mesopore and macropore size distributions were evaluated using the Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method [33], using Roberts algorithm [34] and the standard Carbon Black STSA isotherm with Faas correction. The micropore size distribution was evaluated from the low-pressure part ($10^{-8} < p/p_0 < 0.05$) of the N₂ adsorption isotherm using the Hovarth-Kawazoe method [35].

Raman spectra of WAB-C were obtained using an XploRA™ confocal Raman spectrometer (HORIBA Jobin Yvon, France). The instrument includes an Olympus BX41/51 optical microscope with a 50x magnification objective. Laser (532 nm, 100 mW, class 3B) with intensity controlled to 1% of the original radiation was used. The acquired spectra were scanned 10 times for 10 s at a grating setting of 1200 gr./mm. Spectra were collected from 10 different points. All adjustments (background-baseline comparison, band position labeling) were performed using LabSpec software. Normalized and averaged spectra were calculated in Origin 2019b software.

Attenuated total reflectance (ATR) Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of WAB-C were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ with spectral resolution 4 cm⁻¹ by Nicolet 6700 FT-IR. The spectra were collected in an ATR diamond crystal and evaluated by OMNIC software (baseline and ATR correction).

Chemical composition of WAB-RM and WAB-C was determined semi-quantitatively by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRFS) on the XEPOS (Spectro, Germany) energy dispersion spectrometer. After trituration, the samples were placed in a plastic cuvette with a Mylar protective foil and analysed in He atmosphere.

Total phosphorus was determined in accordance with the ČSN EN ISO 6878 standard using a UV–VIS spectrophotometric method.

Calcium was determined using flame atomic absorption spectrometry. The samples were mineralised using the Ethos UP microwave digestion system and then analysed using the contraAA 700 spectrometer (Analytik Jena). This instrument enables the sequential determination of trace metals (and selected non-metals) and provides a platform for flame-based analytical techniques.

Phase composition and microstructural properties of WAB-C were determined by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis in a reflection mode (Bragg-Brentano geometry) using Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) with detector D/teX Ultra 250 and Cu tube ($\text{Cu}_{K\alpha}$, $\lambda = 0.154059$ nm, 40 kV, 30 mA). Incident and diffracted beam optics were equipped with 5° Soller slits (1 mm). Rotational sample holder (30 rpm) was used to eliminate preferred orientation effect. XRD patterns were collected in a range of $5\text{--}90^\circ 2\theta$ (step size 0.01° ; speed $0.5 \text{ deg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), evaluated using PDXL 2 software (v.2.4.2.0, Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) and compared with database PDF-2, release 2015 (ICDD, Newton Square, USA).

Morphology and surface changes related to different bone types and MW performance were studied using scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan Vega) with tungsten cathode. Micrographs were obtained using combination of secondary electrons (SE) and backscattered electrons (BSE) mode (SE+BSE) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) with an acceleration voltage of 15 keV. Samples before imaging were gold sputtered in order to ensure adequate electron conductivity. Photos were taken from random places of samples to ensure an unbiased examination of the samples (without focusing on unnecessary anomalies or artefacts).

Force field-based molecular modeling was realized in the Materials Studio 4.2 (MS; Biovia, CA, USA) modeling environment. Periodic unit cell of hydroxyapatite ($a = b = 9.4 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.86 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 120^\circ$ [36]) built in the MS/Crystal Builder module was cleaved along (001), (00-1), (100), and (200) planes to obtain periodic surfaces. A top view of the planes is provided in Fig. S2. Carbon was approximated by a graphitic structure [37,38], and periodic surfaces prepared by cutting the unit cell of graphite ($a = b = 2.46 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.67 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 120^\circ$ [36]) along the (001) and (100) planes were also used in this study. While the (001) plane is parallel to the graphite layers, the (100) plane is perpendicular to them. It is the edge of the layers and the edge carbons are terminated by hydrogens. See the top view of the planes in Fig. S2. Periodic unit cell of calcite ($a = b = 4.99 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 17.06 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 120^\circ$ [36]) and calcium oxide ($a = b = c = 4.81 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ [38]) was cleaved along (001), (00-1), (100) planes and (100), (110), (111), (-1-1-1) planes, respectively, to obtain periodic surfaces. A top view of the planes is provided in Fig. S2. After enlarging each surface to $\sim 3 \times 3$ nm, 3D periodic cells were created by adding vacuum slab with a height of 100 \AA . These models of surfaces were denoted as HA(001), HA(00-1), HA(100), HA(200), G(001), G(100), CA(001), CA(00-1), CA(100), CaO(100), CaO(110), CaO(111), and CaO(-1-1-1). Models G(001) and G(100) were also prepared with Ca^{2+} cations. The cations were initially randomly positioned at a distance ≤ 1 nm from the surface. These models were denoted as G(001) Ca^{2+} and G(100) Ca^{2+} . Initial models for studying the interaction with xylenes were prepared by placing xylene molecules in the cells at various random positions and distances from a given surface (up to ~ 1 nm). Parameterization of atoms, i.e. assignment of atomic types and charges, and geometry optimization of the initial models were performed using COMPASS force field [39] in MS/Forcite module. Smart algorithm was used for the optimization with the following convergence criteria for distance, energy and force: $\Delta d = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ \AA}$, $\Delta E = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and $\Delta F = 0.5 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{\AA}^{-1}$, respectively. Number of iteration steps was $5 \cdot 10^5$. External pressure was set to $101,325 \text{ Pa}$.

The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed using the Nexsa G2 Surface Analysis System (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with a monochromatic Al K- α source and a photon energy of

1486.6 eV. All the spectra were measured in the vacuum of 10^{-7} mbar and at the room temperature of 25°C . The analysed area on each sample was spot of $300 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. The survey spectra were measured with pass energy of 100.00 eV and step of 1.0 eV while for the high-resolution spectra were used pass energy of 20.00 eV and step of 0.1 eV . Charge compensation was used for all measurements. The spectra were evaluated with the Avantage 6 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) software.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw feedstock (WAB-RM)

Proteins and fat were found to be the main components of WAB-RM (Table 1). Proteins (determined according to the standard ČSN ISO 1871) and fat (determined by gravimetry), varied in the interval $22.9\text{--}33.1 \text{ wt}\%$ and $2.4\text{--}18.2 \text{ wt}\%$, respectively. Beef bones showed the lowest value of fat. Higher amount of fat and proteins in PB-RM and CB-RM was caused by remains of meat and skin in raw material. CB-RM exhibited lower amount of crude fiber ($\sim 2 \text{ wt}\%$) compared to BF-RM, BB-RM and PB-RM ($\sim 5 \text{ wt}\%$). Sugar ($< 0.3 \text{ wt}\%$) was similar for all samples.

Proximate analysis revealed the highest amount of moisture for BF-RM ($26.3 \text{ wt}\%$). This is due to the absence of drying applied to the boiled bones (see the five times lower moisture for the other samples; Table 2). On the other hand, volatile matter in boiled samples is higher ($40.6\text{--}48.0 \text{ wt}\%$) compared to BF-RM ($32.3 \text{ wt}\%$). The lower ash content in BF-RM is in good agreement with the higher moisture. Amount of fixed carbon is very low for all samples ($3.5\text{--}5.4 \text{ wt}\%$).

Elemental analysis (Table 2) showed the highest amount of C ($17.8\text{--}30.1 \text{ wt}\%$), followed by one order of magnitude lower amount of H ($4.0\text{--}6.2 \text{ wt}\%$) and N ($3.8\text{--}5.6 \text{ wt}\%$), and a negligible amount of S. The source of nitrogen are proteins [39]; see the good correlation of its increasing content (Table 2) with increasing protein content (Table 1), while the $w_{\text{N}}/w_{\text{Protein}}$ mass ratio remains the same ($16.7 \pm 0.5 \text{ wt}\%$).

As for other elements, the most abundant Ca and P as determined by XRF analysis (Table 3) come from hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$), apatite carbonate ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{CO}_3$) and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) [8]. The high content of Ca and P explains high amount of ash and low amount of fixed carbon in WAB-RM (Table 2).

TG curves of WAB-RM samples (Fig. 1a) show that at the temperature of 1000°C , the highest weight loss was achieved for PB-RM ($\sim 57 \text{ wt}\%$), followed by CB-RM ($\sim 55 \text{ wt}\%$) and then BF-RM with BB-RM ($\sim 50 \text{ wt}\%$). Comparison of Fig. 1a and Table 2 shows that the samples with high weight losses are the samples containing the high number of volatiles. DTG curves (Fig. 1b) revealed the termination of the pyrolysis process is at 600°C for samples BF-RM, BB-RM and CB-RM, while for PB-RM the terminal temperature is 950°C . According to DTG curves, pyrolysis has two main stages. The first one ($\sim 25\text{--}200^\circ \text{C}$) corresponds to the removal of moisture and lipids. During the second one ($200\text{--}600^\circ \text{C}$) with a weight loss of $38\text{--}46 \text{ wt}\%$, the DTG curves show several smaller peaks. The highest rate of weight loss ($200\text{--}400^\circ \text{C}$) corresponds to the degradation of organic intermediates. The shoulders observed at 450°C correspond to degradation of bones [3].

Table 1
Organic constituents of waste animal bones (WAB-RM).

	Protein	Fat	Fiber	Carbohydrate*	Sugar**
	wt%				
BF-RM	22.9	2.4	4.5	0.5	< 0.3
BB-RM	26.8	10.1	4.9	0.5	< 0.3
PB-RM	27.7	18.2	4.9	0.5	< 0.3
CB-RM	33.1	16.3	2.3	< 0.9	< 0.3

*starch + invert; **after inversion

Table 2

Proximate analysis and elemental analysis of waste animal bones (WAB-RM).

	Moisture	Volatile wt%	Fixed carbon	Ash	C	H	N	S
BF-RM	26.3	32.3	3.5	37.9	17.8	6.2	3.8	0.2
BB-RM	5.4	40.6	3.6	50.4	20.2	4.0	4.3	0.1
PB-RM	6.2	48.0	5.0	40.8	27.5	4.8	4.8	0.2
CB-RM	2.9	43.6	5.4	48.1	30.1	4.5	5.6	0.3

Table 3

XRF analysis of waste animal bones (WAB-RM).

	Ca	P	Cl	S	Si	K
BF-RM	30.1	6.1	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.5
BB-RM	38.8	10.8	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.0
PB-RM	31.0	8.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.5
CB-RM	31.8	8.8	1.2	1.0	0.1	0.5

Mg detected below 0.002 wt%

3.2. Microwave pyrolysis product yields

The solid (bonechar, WAB-C), liquid and gas phase yields obtained by MW pyrolysis of WAB-RM (Fig. 2a-d) show that the different MW powers (200, 400, 600 W) are not as crucial as the bone type itself. Average solid phase yield is 32.7 ± 0.9 wt% for BF-RM (Figs. 2a), 59.7 ± 2.4 wt% for BB-RM (Fig. 2b), 38 ± 1.5 wt% for PB-RM (Fig. 2c), and 52 ± 2.1 wt% for CB-RM (Fig. 2d). Pyrolyses of PB-RM at 400 W and CB-RM at 600 W were not completed due to a hot spot formation and subsequent breakage of the glass vessel. Therefore, mass balance of this sample is not shown in Fig. 2c,d. Incomplete pyrolyses of these two samples is also confirmed by high volatile matter 18.1 wt% and 39.3 wt %, respectively (see Table 4). For this reason, these two samples were not considered for comparison with the other bonechars in this study.

With regard to the phase of the products, the yields (averages for all MW powers; Fig. 2) of individual WAB-RM can be summarized as follows: the highest yield of solid, liquid and gas phase was found for BB-RM (59.7 ± 2.4 wt%), BF-RM (39 ± 1.56 wt%) and CB-RM (44.5 ± 1.8 wt%), respectively. The highest yield of solid phase in BB-RM agrees well with the high fixed carbon and ash content (the sum is 54 wt%, see Table 2). The highest liquid and gas phase yield can be attributed to the volatile content (32.3 wt% for BF-RM and 43.6 wt% for PB-RM; Table 2). In terms of the highest adsorbent yield (solid phase), the most suitable are boiled bones in the following order: BB (~ 60 wt%) > CB (~ 52 wt%) > PB (~ 38 wt%). In the case of fresh bones (BF), the adsorbent yield was significantly lower (~ 33 wt% solid phase) and a large amount of liquid phase was also produced (~ 33 wt%). The high

amount of liquid phase in fresh bones is due to fat, protein and meat residues not removed by cooking and released as liquid phase during pyrolysis.

3.3. Characterization of bonechar

With the exception of PB-C;400 and CB-C;600 (see 3.2 for the cause), the amounts of volatiles are in a narrow range (4.4–9.0 wt%) suggesting that each MW power used (200, 400 and 600 W) is sufficient for complete pyrolysis (Table 4). Proximate analysis of bonechars (Table 4) shows that the amount of ash generally increases at the expense of fixed carbon. If the incompletely pyrolyzed samples PB-C;400 and CB-C;600 are excluded from the comparison with the other bonechar, then the total amount of ash and fixed carbon (Table 4) is stable for all samples (93.4 ± 1.8 wt%). The higher amount of ash in bonechars compared to chars produced by MW from different raw feedstocks, e.g. waste scrap tyres (10.7–31.3 wt% [37]), biomass (11.1 wt% [40]) or chicken cartilage (27.7–40.1 wt% [41]) can be explained by the presence of inorganic apatite, calcium carbonate, etc. in raw bones.

The elemental analysis of bonechars (Table 4) revealed significantly higher carbon content compared to nitrogen and hydrogen. If the incompletely pyrolyzed samples PB-C;400 and CB-C;600 are excluded, the order of samples according to the average C and average N content is PB-C (~ 24 wt%) > CB-C (~ 22 wt%) > BF-C (~ 19 wt%) > BB-C (~ 12 wt%) and PB-C (~ 2.8 wt%) > BF-C (~ 2.6 wt%) > CB-C (~ 2.4 wt%) > BB-C (~ 2.0 wt%), respectively.

Component analysis (XRF, UV-VIS, AAS) (Table 5) shows that the BB-C with the lowest amount of C and N exhibits the highest amount of Ca and P, while the PB-C having the highest amount of C and N exhibits the lowest amount of P, and the Ca amount similar to BF-C and CB-C (compare Tables 5 and 4). In general, the C+N content is at the expense of Ca+P (and vice versa) originating from the mineral phases in raw bones. The stoichiometric molar ratio Ca/P for hydroxyapatite is usually 1.67 [17]. MW pyrolysis had little effect on the Ca/P molar ratio. The values remained constant at ~ 1.5 . The small variation in Ca/P values in WAB-C may be due to the presence of the other minerals or minor calcium compounds such as oxide, hydroxide or carbonate forms [17].

Fig. 1. TG curves (a) and DTG curves (b) of waste raw bones (WAB-RM).

Fig. 2. Mass balance of individual pyrolytic phases from microwave of (a) BF-RM, (b) BB-RM, (c) PB-RM, (d) CB-RM, at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

Table 4

Proximate and ultimate analysis of bonechar (WAB-C) prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

	Moisture	Volatile matter wt%	Fixed carbon	Ash	C	H	N	S	O
BF-C;200	1.2	7.1	16.0	75.7	19.2	0.3	2.8	0.1	77.6
BF-C;400	1.6	4.9	17.0	76.6	18.6	0.3	2.7	0.1	78.3
BF-C;600	1.5	5.5	15.7	77.3	18.3	0.9	2.4	0.1	78.3
BB-C;200	2.3	6.6	10.4	80.8	13.3	1.3	2.0	0.1	83.3
BB-C;400	1.6	4.7	9.9	83.9	13.3	0.5	2.0	0.1	84.1
BB-C;600	1.6	4.4	6.9	87.1	10.1	0.4	1.9	0.1	87.5
PB-C;200	3.3	7.6	22.1	67.0	23.3	1.0	2.6	0.1	73.0
PB-C;400*	2.5	18.1	19.8	59.7	27.6	1.9	3.2	0.1	67.2
PB-C;600	3.3	9.0	22.0	65.8	24.8	1.0	3.0	0.1	71.1
CB-C;200	0.1	4.5	21.2	74.2	22.5	1.8	2.5	0.1	73.1
CB-C;400	0.7	4.8	19.3	75.2	20.7	0.4	2.2	0.1	76.6
CB-C;600*	1.5	39.3	11.0	48.3	34.4	3.0	4.9	0.2	57.5

*incomplete pyrolysis (not considered for comparison with other bonechars)

XRD analysis (Fig. 3) revealed hexagonal hydroxyapatite as the main phase in all bonechars, which is in good agreement with literature data [12,42]. Calcite phase was also discovered in bonechars prepared from beef boiled bones and chicken boiled bones (except CB-C;200). Crystalline graphite would be expected to be present in bonechar [43], but its presence was not detected by XRD. It is evident from Fig. 3 that with increasing MW power from 200 to 400 W, the reflection width decreased and the intensity increased (except for PB-C), indicating an increase in crystal size (see Table 6). At 400 W power, the crystal size reached its maximum value and as the MW power increased to 600 W, the crystal size decreased. As expected, the incompletely pyrolyzed samples (PB-C;400 and CB-C;600) exhibit the lowest crystallinity of the hydroxyapatite phase. Due to the low degree of crystallinity of the phases present in bone char, the presence of other phases (e.g. CaO) is also possible. However, the crystalline bands of these other phases tend to overlap, and therefore their presence cannot be confirmed or refuted.

SEM analysis of WAB-C at 200, 400 and 600 W (Fig. S3) revealed that the surface of all WAB-C is characterized by a large number of small gaps, except for incompletely pyrolyzed samples PB-C;400 (Fig. S3h) and CB-C;600 (Fig. S3l). On the surface of these bonechars, there are small particles of the same origin. These particles may be the non-pyrolyzed part of the raw material (tar) covering small gaps of bonechar. WAB-C shows stacked-layer meso/macropore structure typical for hydroxyapatite [8]. As shown in SEM images, PB-C (Fig. S3g,i) and CB-C (Fig. S3j,k) show a 3D hierarchical honeycomb porous structure with interconnected pores containing open pores and channels with the most abundant diameter of 15 nm (see Fig. 5). On the other hand, the surface of BF-C (Fig. S3a-c) and BB-C (Fig. S3d-f) is rough with an undefined geometry with larger open pores and channels with wider pores distribution (see Fig. 5b,d). It is also evident, that micropore power did not affect WAB-C porosity (except incomplete pyrolyzed PB-C;400 and CB-C;600). A lower amount of the total pore volume is also evident for

Table 5

Component analysis of bonechar (WAB-C) prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

	Ca	S	P	Cl	Si	K	Ca/P**
	wt%						
BF-C;200	24.4	0.1	13.0	0.6	0.2	1.4	1.5
BF-C;400	25.7	0.2	12.7	0.4	0.2	1.0	1.6
BF-C;600	26.4	0.2	12.9	0.5	0.2	1.2	1.6
BB-C;200	29.4	0.2	15.2	0.3	0.2	0.1	1.5
BB-C;400	28.8	0.2	14.7	0.2	0.2	0.1	1.5
BB-C;600	31.3	0.2	15.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	1.6
PB-C;200	23.6	0.3	12.0	0.6	0.1	0.5	1.5
PB-C;400*	20.5	0.3	10.5	0.7	0.1	0.7	1.5
PB-C;600	22.5	0.3	13.0	0.6	0.1	0.6	1.3
CB-C;200	21.2	0.4	11.7	1.2	0.1	0.8	1.4
CB-C;400	24.0	0.3	13.0	1.1	0.1	0.8	1.4
CB-C;600*	16.2	0.3	8.9	0.9	0.1	0.7	1.4

*incomplete pyrolysis (not considered for comparison with other bonechars);

**molar ratio; Mg detected below 0.002 wt%

BB-C;600 (Table 6, Fig. S3d-f), probably due to the sintering at the high MW power of 600 W.

Hydroxyapatite was also detected by FTIR spectra (Fig. 4) containing all the characteristic bands in the region below 1800 cm^{-1} . Vibration of $-\text{PO}_4$ functional group is connected to the bands at 1024 , 960 , 600 , 557 cm^{-1} . The bands intensities and positions correspond to the spectra of bones with low carbonate content [44]. Small doublet (1450 and 1403 cm^{-1}) corresponds to the $-\text{CO}_3$ vibration, bands at 877 and 698 cm^{-1} to the calcite. There is also small shoulder at 1081 cm^{-1} which can be ascribed to the presence of francolite [44]. In the case of PB-C;400 (Fig. 4c) and CB-C;600 (Fig. 4d), the bands below 3000 cm^{-1} corresponding to vibrations of C-H bonds in $-\text{CH}_2$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ groups [45] suggest the incomplete pyrolysis, as expected. However, these bands are present also in FTIR spectra of the CB-C;B200 (Fig. 4d). This can be explained by the highest content of proteins in raw material (see CB-RM

in Table 1), which were not fully degraded at 200 W. There is very small band around 470 cm^{-1} (marked with arrow in the Fig. 4) and according to the literature [46] can be connected to the presence of the Ca-O band.

Raman spectroscopy did not provide information about the presence of hydroxyapatite, only carbon was detected (Fig. S4). The spectra show two main bands at ~ 1585 and $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Denoted as G band and D band, respectively, they are connected to the graphitic character of carbon (sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms) and the disorder in graphitic structure, respectively [47].

The shape of the spectra, specifically the merging of both bands to form a high saddle, suggests the presence of amorphous phase containing sp^3 -hybridized carbon atoms [48]. It should be noted that the presence of amorphous carbon does not exclude the presence of G band. Amorphous carbon also exhibits G band, which originates from locally ordered graphitic domains inherently present in the amorphous phase [49]. Overall, it can be concluded that the samples contain both graphitic and amorphous form.

Strong fluorescence was observed in all samples, especially in the case of those incompletely pyrolyzed (PB-C;400 and CB-C;600) as well as CB-C;200 (for which FTIR also showed vibrations of C-H bonds in $-\text{CH}_2$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ groups, see Fig. 4). Only fluorescence was detected for the CB-C;600, so the spectrum is missing. Raman spectra of CB-C;200 and PB-C;400 could not be obtained with no fluorescence at all 10 points as for the other samples, so the average Raman spectra of these two samples were created from a lower number of spectra. Ratios I_D/I_G , calculated from intensities of D and G bands, were found to be ~ 1 for all samples (Table 6).

Fluorescence may also be one of the reasons for the absence of characteristic Raman bands of hydroxyapatite [50]. Although the fluorescence background was numerically reduced during spectral processing, it cannot be excluded that a weak hydroxyapatite signal may have been masked by the fluorescence contribution. Another possible reason is the layer of carbon on the hydroxyapatite, which can significantly weaken or completely suppress the Raman signal originating

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of bonechars prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

Table 6

Textural properties and parameters of the Raman peaks of bonechar (WAB-C) prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

	Textural parameters		Raman spectrometry		XRD		HA crystal size***
	S_{BET}	V_{net}	$I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$	Number of points	Phase composition		
					HA**	Calcite	
	$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	$\text{mm}_{\text{liq}}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	-	-	-	-	nm
BF-C;200	100	252	1.03	8	✓	x	16
BF-C;400	91	245	1.06	10	✓✓	x	31
BF-C;600	91	243	1.00	10	✓	x	22
BB-C;200	121	278	1.01	7	✓	✓	12
BB-C;400	99	246	1.11	10	✓	✓	34
BB-C;600	68	257	1.07	9	✓	✓	16
PB-C;200	92	194	1.09	5	✓	x	31
PB-C;400*	73	136	0.97	2	✓	x	24
PB-C;600	93	187	1.08	9	✓	x	5
CB-C;200	78	169	1.03	5	✓	x	16
CB-C;400	82	177	1.00	8	✓	✓	19
CB-C;600*	49	67	nd	0	✓	✓	5

* incomplete pyrolysis (not considered for comparison with other bonechars); ** HA = hydroxyapatite; *** Lc=lateral size; nd = not determined

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of bonechars prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

from the hydroxyapatite. It is also necessary to take into account the possible inhomogeneous distribution of hydroxyapatite. This, together with the spot measurements, could have caused the failure to find an area with a below-average carbon content and a sufficient content of pure hydroxyapatite. Most likely, a combination of all the above-mentioned factors contributed to the absence of detectable hydroxyapatite bands in the recorded Raman spectra. However, the absence of the characteristic PO_4^{3-} band in Raman spectra ($\sim 940 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is not an unknown phenomenon, as can be seen e.g. in the study by Liu et al. [51].

Nitrogen physisorption isotherms and size-distribution of macro and mesopores for BF-C (a,b), BB-C (c,d), PB-C (e,f), and CB-C (g,h) are shown in Fig. 5. Specific surface area, S_{BET} , and total pore volume, V_{net} , are listed in Table 6. Bonechars are characterized by the II and IV isotherm type with minimum N_2 uptake ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3(\text{STP}) \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) at $p/p_0 < 0.05$ and narrow step hysteresis loop (confirming presence of

macropores) at higher relative pressure (confirming presence of mesopores) $p/p_0 = 0.1-1$ for BF-C (Fig. 5a) and at $p/p_0 = 0.4-1$ for BB-C, PB-C and CB-C (Fig. 5c,e,g) which is characteristic for meso/macroporous materials without micropores. Therefore, the V_{net} ($67-278 \text{ mm}_{\text{liq}}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and S_{BET} ($49-121 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) values represent predominantly volume and areas of meso/macropore surface with the most frequent mesopores of $\sim 20 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 5b,d,f,h). Reduction of S_{BET} and V_{net} observed for BF-C and BB-C at MW power of 600 W (Table 6) is probably caused by fusion or sintering of pores, as well as the ash in bonechar, which could fill the micropores and block the access of pyrolytic gas [17,39]. According to Patel et al. [17], the specific surface area of bovine and bull bones conventionally pyrolyzed in the temperature range of 400 – 600 °C decreases with increasing temperature and retention time. At high temperature, the small pores can intermingle and form pores with large diameter. The porous structure of bonechar could also be influenced by the Ca/P molar ratio. An increase in the S_{BET} of bonechar and

Fig. 5. Nitrogen isotherms at 77 K (a,c,e,g) and mesopore-macropore- size (b,d,f,h) of bonechar prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

synthesized hydroxyapatite with increasing Ca/P molar ratio has been reported [17,52]. However, this is not consistent with our results, where S_{BET} decreased with increasing Ca/P molar ratio (Fig. 6, left). However, S_{BET} increase slightly with increasing crystal size of hydroxyapatite (Fig. 6, right), indicating that the presence of the carbon phase contributes to increasing the porosity of the bonechar.

It is clear and necessary to remember that bonechar is a composite material. The dominant part (67–87 wt%, Table 4) of it is the inorganic component composed of hydroxyapatite and calcite (Table 6). The minority part (7–22 wt%, Table 4) of it is composed of carbon.

3.4. Xylene adsorption capacity of bonechar

According to adsorption capacities (1^{st} measurement; Table 7), the bonechars can be sorted in descending order as follows: BF-C;600 > BF-C;200 > CB-C;400 > BB-C;200 > BB-C;400 > CB-C;200 > BB-C;600 > PB-C;200 \approx PB-C;600. If only the type of bone is taken into account, then the order corresponds to BF-C > BB-C \approx CB-B > PB-C.

The lowest values of adsorption capacities (1^{st} and 2^{nd} measurement in Table 7) of PB-C;400* and CB-C;600* could be explained by incomplete pyrolysis when volatiles block pores of bonechars and occupy them instead of xylene. From this reason, these two bonechars were not further considered for comparison.

After the 1^{st} measurement, the bonechars were regenerated by pre-heated air (160 °C) for 12 h, and the second adsorption experiment

Table 7

Xylene adsorption capacity of investigated bonechar (WAB-C) prepared by MW pyrolysis at 200, 400 and 600 W for 30 min.

Material	Xylene adsorption capacity		
	1st measurement	After desorption/ 2nd measurement	Re-use
	$\text{mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$		%
BF-C;200	45.0	33.0	73
BF-C;400	nd	nd	nd
BF-C;600	47.7	30.2	63
BB-C;200	22.8	16.0	70
BB-C;400	20.5	18.1	88
BB-C;600	16.9	14.1	83
PB-C;200	13.8	9.9	72
PB-C;400*	4.2	3.4	81
PB-C;600	13.5	9.6	71
CB-C;200	18.0	5.1	28
CB-C;400	23.5	11.8	50
CB-C;600*	4.6	3.6	78

* incomplete pyrolysis (not considered for comparison with other bonechars); nd = not determined

was performed (see After desorption/2nd measurement in Table 7). The regeneration process did not alter the properties of the bone char, as documented in Table S1 of the Supplementary material.

If only the type of bone is taken into account, then the order is almost

Fig. 6. The effect of Ca/P molar ratio (a) and crystal size of hydroxyapatite (b) on porous structure (S_{BET}) of all investigated bonechars.

unchanged compared to the 1st measurement BF-C > BB-C > PB-C ≈ CB-C. However, the order of individual bonechars differs from the 1st measurement: BF-C;200 > BF-C;600 > BB-C;400 > BB-C;200 > BB-C;600 > CB-C;400 > PB-C;200 ≈ PB-C;600 > CB-C;200. It is evident that the CB-C;200 exhibits the largest decrease in xylene adsorption capacity of all samples and its capacity in the 2nd measurement represents only ~30% of the capacity determined in the 1st measurement (see percentages in the Re-use column in Table 7). BB-C;400 showed the highest rate of retention of original capacity (~90%; Table 7). Concerning the re-use (see Table 7), BB-C bonechars can be considered the most suitable xylene adsorbent. For all adsorbent materials, their re-use is a key parameter to assess their potential technological applications; ideally, in fact, the adsorption of the pollutants should be reversible, to regenerate the material for use in subsequent cycles [15].

The CB-C;200 exhibiting the lowest re-use value is characterized by high amount of fixed carbon and least developed porous structure. On the contrary, BB-C;400 with high re-use value shows developed porous structure and low amount of fixed carbon. This finding could confirm the formation of strong interactions between xylene and fixed carbon in the bonechar, and weak interaction between xylene and bonechar with mesopores.

One of the most widely used, effective and environmentally viable regeneration method of adsorbents is thermal regeneration, which has many advantages, such as high efficiency, more regeneration cycles, simple operation and no use of chemicals [53]. The thermal regeneration of fluoride saturated bovine bonechar, studied by Nigri *et al.* [53], showed that bovine bonechar treated at 400 °C kept almost 60% of the original adsorption capacity. Our results of thermal regeneration of BB-C in pre-heated air (160 °C) shows much higher regeneration value (70–88%; Table 7).

BF-C;200 and BF-C;600 have the highest adsorption capacity, but their porous structure ($S_{\text{BET}} \approx 95 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) is not the most developed (Fig. 7). On the other hand, BB-C;200 and BB-C;400 exhibiting lower adsorption capacity and at the same time have the higher S_{BET} value (99–121 $\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$). It means that dependence of the adsorption capacity on porous structure is not unambiguous and straightforward. Nevertheless, Piccirillo [15] and Patel *et al.* [17] agree that also graphitic carbon is effective for the adsorption of organic molecules. Therefore, with increasing amount of fixed carbon and its graphitic structure (*i.e.* decreasing $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio), an increase in adsorption capacity can be expected. This is in a quite good agreement with our results: BF-C showing the highest adsorption capacity (~47 $\text{mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$; Table 7, Fig. 7), high amount of fixed carbon (~16 wt%; Table 4, Fig. 7), and the lowest $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio (1.00–1.06; Table 6, Fig. 7) and does not show the highest S_{BET} value (Table 6, Fig. 7). On the other hand, BB-C has the highest value of S_{BET} , but on the other hand the lowest amount of fixed carbon content (~9 wt%, Table 4) with low graphitization ($I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}} \approx 1.1$, Table 6). Xylene

adsorption capacity of BB-C is quite comparable to PB-C and CB-C (Table 7, Fig. 7). CB-C bonechars are characterized by large amount of fixed carbon (~20 wt%; Table 4, Fig. 7) with high graphitization ($I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}} \approx 1$, Table 6) even though the porosity is the lowest ($S_{\text{BET}} = 78\text{--}82 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and PB-C is shows the highest fixed carbon content (~22 wt%; Table 4, Fig. 7) but with lower graphitization ($I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}} \approx 1.1$, Table 6) and medium porosity ($S_{\text{BET}} \approx 93 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$).

The xylene adsorption capacity is not the same for all bonechars produced from boiled bones (BB, PB and CB). Interestingly, bonechars containing surface calcite have slightly higher values of xylene adsorption capacity (BB-C and CB-C;400, Table 6 and Table 7) than others.

As mentioned above, the effectiveness of xylene adsorption capacity can be attributed to the synergistic effect of both the porous structure and graphitization, as well as other bonechar properties. For this reason, XPS analysis was performed to compare selected bonechars prepared under the same conditions (200 W) in order to clarify these factors (see Tables S2–S3 and Figs. S5–S7). The results indicate that the highest presence of $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ bonds (6.2 at% for BF-C;200, fitted from HR spectra of C1s; Table S2) and CaO (72.2 at% of Ca present as CaO for BF-C;200, fitted from HR spectra of Ca2p; Table S2) have the greatest influence on the adsorption capacity of xylene. From our previous studies [37,54], we already know that the mechanism of xylene adsorption occurs by $\pi\text{-}\pi$ bonds, and that the size and charge of cations present also have a key effect on the xylene adsorption capacity. This is consistent with the current data (Tables 6, 7, S2, S3). Conversely, the presence of oxygen-containing polar bonds (33.4 at% for BB-C;200, fitted from HR spectra of O1s; Table S2) has a negative effect on the adsorption of non-polar xylene.

The fact that the mixture of xylene (o-xylene (39.8%), m-xylene (18.4%), p-xylene (26.9%), and ethylbenzene (16.9%)) is constant throughout all experiments means that any potential deviation caused by the presence of ethylbenzene remains the same for all the bonechars tested. This keeps the performance trends same. The most efficient bonechars demonstrated xylene adsorption capacities of between 45 and 47 $\text{mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$, whereas other samples exhibited significantly lower values of between 13 and 24 $\text{mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$. These results clearly differentiate between the performance of the materials and remain representative of industrial conditions, despite the multicomponent nature of the technical xylene mixture.

Xylene adsorption was also studied using molecular modeling. Average interaction energy (E_{int}) for xylenes and hydroxyapatite was found slightly lower, *i.e.* stronger ($-15.10 \pm 5.45 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-HA}_{\text{AVG}}$ in Table 8), compared to average E_{int} for xylenes and carbon surfaces ($-13.62 \pm 2.47 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-G}_{\text{AVG}}$ in Table 8) and average E_{int} for xylenes and calcite surfaces ($-12.26 \pm 5.43 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-CA}_{\text{AVG}}$ in Table 8). However, the strongest average E_{int} is exhibited by xylenes on carbon surfaces in the presence of Ca^{2+} cations ($-24.74 \pm 10.84 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-G}_{\text{CA}_{\text{AVG}}}$ in Table 8). The high standard deviation is due to the notable difference in the E_{int} values for the surface and edge of graphitic carbon ($-35.34 \pm 2.68 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and $-14.15 \pm 1.90 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-G}(001)\text{Ca}^{2+}$ and $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-G}(100)\text{Ca}^{2+}$, respectively, in Table 8). It has been previously shown [55] that metal cations can mediate a very strong interaction between the aromatic rings of the graphitic structure and xylene, and the present results are consistent with that. When anchored on the surface, the Ca^{2+} cations are directly accessible to xylene molecules, leading to a strong interaction. In the case of the edge, Ca^{2+} cations tend to penetrate between layers and move away from xylenes, weakening the interaction. The results therefore indicate that Ca^{2+} cations on the surface could play a role in the adsorption. Optimized models showing the described behaviour are provided in Supplementary material (Fig. S8). The second strongest average E_{int} was found for xylenes on calcium oxide surfaces ($-21.49 \pm 2.80 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $X_{\text{AVG}}\text{-CaO}_{\text{AVG}}$ in Table 8). It can be stated that the presence of Ca^{2+} cations and calcium oxide in bonechars enhances the adsorption of xylene. Molecular modeling thus supports the results of XPS analysis. Micropores (diameter <2 nm) which were previously

Fig. 7. Effect of fixed carbon content, ash content, ratio $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ and specific surface area (S_{BET}) on maximum adsorption xylene capacity (xylene).

Table 8

Interaction energy (in kcal/mol) for each xylene, i.e. OX, MX, PX, and each HA, G, G with Ca^{2+} , CAL, and CaO plane, i.e. HA(001), HA(00-1), HA(100), HA(200), G(001), G(100), G(001) Ca^{2+} , G(100) Ca^{2+} , CAL(001), CAL(00-1), CAL(100), CaO(100), CaO(110), CaO(111), CaO(-1-1-1). Average values for all xylenes (X_{AVG}), HA planes (HA_{AVG}), G planes (G_{AVG} , $G_{\text{Ca}^{2+}_{\text{AVG}}}$), CAL planes (CAL_{AVG}), and CaO planes (CaO_{AVG}) are also listed. More negative interaction energy means stronger xylene-substrate interaction.

	OX	MX	PX	X_{AVG}
HA(001)	-12.43 ± 6.25	-17.97 ± 3.89	-15.40 ± 5.63	-15.27 ± 5.81
HA(00-1)	-7.11 ± 1.44	-15.82 ± 5.54	-17.39 ± 5.28	-13.44 ± 6.38
HA(100)	-13.76 ± 1.97	-15.51 ± 1.16	-12.15 ± 1.87	-13.80 ± 2.19
HA(200)	-16.78 ± 5.23	-21.27 ± 0.96	-15.60 ± 5.96	-17.88 ± 5.22
HA_{AVG}	-12.52 ± 5.51	-17.64 ± 4.16	-15.13 ± 5.31	-15.10 ± 5.45
G(001)	-15.74 ± 0.24	-16.16 ± 0.11	-16.11 ± 0.12	-16.00 ± 0.25
G(100)	-10.59 ± 0.46	-11.12 ± 0.88	-11.99 ± 0.60	-11.23 ± 0.88
G_{AVG}	-13.17 ± 2.60	-13.64 ± 2.60	-14.05 ± 2.10	-13.62 ± 2.47
G(001) Ca^{2+}	-34.84 ± 1.81	-35.29 ± 3.34	-35.88 ± 2.56	-35.34 ± 2.68
G(100) Ca^{2+}	-12.88 ± 1.69	-14.14 ± 1.25	-15.45 ± 1.77	-14.15 ± 1.90
$G_{\text{Ca}^{2+}_{\text{AVG}}}$	-23.86 ± 11.12	-24.71 ± 10.87	-25.66 ± 10.45	-24.74 ± 10.84
CAL(001)	-8.86 ± 1.08	-10.63 ± 1.40	-8.98 ± 2.05	-9.49 ± 1.76
CAL(00-1)	-7.72 ± 0.30	-7.51 ± 0.11	-7.70 ± 0.47	-7.65 ± 0.34
CAL(100)	-18.78 ± 0.88	-19.45 ± 1.34	-20.69 ± 0.86	-19.64 ± 1.31
CAL_{AVG}	-11.79 ± 5.03	-12.53 ± 5.18	-12.46 ± 5.99	-12.26 ± 5.43
CaO(100)	-23.73 ± 0.40	-24.40 ± 0.35	-24.38 ± 0.24	-24.17 ± 0.46
CaO(110)	-21.88 ± 0.33	-21.06 ± 1.20	-21.77 ± 0.72	-21.57 ± 0.91
CaO(111)	-22.89 ± 0.24	-23.21 ± 0.33	-23.47 ± 0.26	-23.19 ± 0.36
CaO(-1-1-1)	-17.01 ± 0.62	-17.15 ± 0.26	-16.90 ± 0.41	-17.02 ± 0.46
CaO_{AVG}	-21.38 ± 2.64	-21.46 ± 2.84	-21.63 ± 2.92	-21.49 ± 2.80

Table 9

Comparison of xylene adsorption capacity (from gas phase) of chars, activated carbons prepared from different raw materials by microwave pyrolysis and commercial carbon blacks.

	Raw material	Pyrolysis conditions	Carbon adsorption capacity ($\text{mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Ref.
Char (without activation)	Chicken cartilage	400 W, 40 min	2–6	[38]
	Scrap tyres	440 W, 25 min Two step pyrolysis 440 W, 15–90 min	11–15	[34]
	Corn cob:scrap tyres mass ratio 4:1	600 W, 30 min	~4	[52]
	Waste animal bones	200, 400, 600 W 30 min	14–48	This study
Activated carbon (with activation)	Chicken cartilage	K_2CO_3 , KOH	164–228	[38]
	Scrap tyres	KOH	27	[34]
	Corn cob:scrap tyres mass ratio 4:1	KOH, ZnCl_2 , K_2CO_3 , NaOH	3–40	[52]
Commercial coal Resorbent s.r.o.	MAC6 D40 CZ	Black coal	214	[34]
	MAC6 I K_2CO_3 5%	Activated black coal	150	This study
	MAC6 I KOH 5%	Activated black coal	150	This study

shown to be a key structural factor for high adsorption capacity (up to $\sim 117 \text{ mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ [37]) and in which case the interaction was also very strong (up to $-34.70 \text{ kcal} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ [37]) are absent in these bonechars (see 3.3.).

Table 9 shows comparison of xylene adsorption capacities from the gas phase for chars/activated carbons prepared by MW pyrolysis of different raw materials. The last row of the Table 9 shows the xylene adsorption capacity of the commercial carbons supplied by company Resorbent, s.r.o. It can be seen that bonechar obtained from boiled bones (BB-C, PB-C and CB-C) in this study has the highest xylene adsorption capacity compared to other chars prepared without activation and comparable xylene adsorption capacity with activated carbon prepared from scrap tyres with KOH. In our study, however, the adsorption capacity of bonechars prepared from fresh bones (BF-C) is (i) higher than that of all chars prepared and activated carbon produced from scrap tyres with KOH and (ii) comparable to activated carbon prepared by copyrolysis. Nevertheless, adsorption capacity of activated carbon from chicken cartilage and commercial carbon black was not exceeded. These activated and commercial carbons show high microporosity [41] and contain metal cations (K^+ , Na^+ and Zn^{+2}) with different charge and size [55] positively influencing the xylene adsorption capacity.

4. Conclusion

This study is one of the few that deals with preparation of bonechar as a xylene adsorbent using MW pyrolysis of different types of animal waste bones (beef, pork, and chicken). Bonechar is, in fact, a composite material composed of dominant inorganic and minor carbon material. The MW power does not affect bones pyrolysis and pyrolytic yields as the type of raw animal waste bones treated. Beef boiled bones gives the highest yield of solid ($\sim 60 \text{ wt}\%$), beef fresh bones liquid ($\sim 40 \text{ wt}\%$), and chicken boiled bones gas ($\sim 45 \text{ wt}\%$). All bonechars are mesoporous-macroporous solids differentiated with Ca/P molar ratio in crystalline hydroxyapatite, contributing to its increased meso-macroporosity. Bonechars prepared from fresh beef bones show the highest xylene adsorption capacity ($\sim 46 \text{ mg}_{\text{xylene}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), while those prepared from boiled beef bones show the highest re-use ($\approx 80\%$). Besides porous structure, also the amount of fixed carbon, graphitization, and the presence of CaO and Ca^{2+} metal cations could be one of the factors determining the xylene adsorption capacity. The most efficient bonechars show the medium porosity ($S_{\text{BET}} \approx 95 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), but high fixed carbon ($\sim 16 \text{ wt}\%$), high graphitization ($I_D/I_G \approx 1.00\text{--}1.06$), and high CaO surface content ($\sim 72 \text{ at}\%$ of Ca present as CaO). Based on xylene

sorption results is evident that calcite-containing bonechars perform better, due to the presence of Ca^{2+} cations, as indicated by molecular modeling results.

Although bonechar prepared from fresh beef bones exhibits the highest xylene adsorption capacity, bonechar made from boiled beef bones is more practical to produce with respect to its higher solid yield, greater reusability, and available sources for its production such e.g. canteens, cookhouses, and restaurants.

The results yielded in this study provide a basis for future research on the production of activated bonechars. Such research should lead to improvement of the texture (porosity) and structure (graphitization, presence of metal cations) of bonechars, i.e. parameters that have been identified to be crucial for xylene adsorption.

Data availability

Open research data following those FAIR principles will be available after manuscript acceptance on Zenodo: DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17142121. Pre-print is available on-line: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7807256/v1>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zuzana Jankovská: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pavλίna Peikertová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jaromír Bojko:** Resources. **Lenka Matějová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Petr Saks:** Resources.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

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Data availability

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